

Fuzzy Subalgebras and Fuzzy Ideals of BCI-Algebras with Operators

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Abstract—The aim of this paper is to introduce the concepts of fuzzy subalgebras, fuzzy ideals and fuzzy quotient algebras of BCI-algebras with operators, and to investigate their basic properties.

Keywords—BCI-algebras, BCI-algebras with operators, fuzzy subalgebras, fuzzy ideals, fuzzy quotient algebras.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE fuzzy set is a generalization of the classical set and it has been applied to many mathematical branches such as groups, rings, ideals and obtained many theories about fuzzy set since Zadeh [13] first raised the concept of fuzzy set in 1965.

BCK/BCI-algebras are two classes of logical algebras, which were introduced by Imai and Iseki [1], [2]. In 1991, Xi [3] applied the concept of fuzzy sets to BCK-algebras, since then fuzzy BCK/BCI-algebras have been extensively investigated by several researchers. Jun et al. [4], [5] introduced the concepts of fuzzy positive implicative ideals and fuzzy commutative ideals of BCK-algebras. Meng et al. [6] introduced the concept of fuzzy implicative ideals of BCK-algebras. Jun et al. [7] introduced the concept of commutative ideals of BCI-algebras, Liu and Meng [9], [10] introduced the concepts of fuzzy positive implicative ideals and fuzzy implicative ideals of BCI-algebras. In 1993, Zheng [8] defined operators in BCK-algebras and introduced the concept of BCI-algebras with operators and gave some isomorphism theorems of it. Next, Liu [12] introduced the universality property of direct products of BCI-algebras. In 2002, Liu [11] introduced the concept of the fuzzy quotient algebras of BCI-algebras.

In this paper, we introduce the definitions of fuzzy subalgebras, fuzzy ideals and fuzzy quotient algebras of BCI-algebras with operators, Moreover, the basic properties were discussed and many results have been obtained, which enriches the theory of BCK/BCI-algebras.

II. PRELIMINARIES

We recall some definitions and propositions which will be needed.

An algebra $\langle X; *, 0 \rangle$ of type (2,0) is called a BCI-algebra, if

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it satisfies the following conditions:

$$BCI-(1) ((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) = 0,$$

$$BCI-(2) (x * (x * y)) * y = 0, \quad BCI-(3) x * x = 0,$$

$$BCI-(4) x * y = 0 \text{ and } y * x = 0 \text{ imply } x = y,$$

for all $x, y, z \in X$. We can define $x * y = 0$ if and only if $x \leq y$, then the above conditions can be written as:

1. $(x * y) * (x * z) \leq z * y$,
2. $x * (x * y) \leq y$,
3. $x \leq x$,
4. $x \leq y$ and $y \leq x$ imply $x = y$,

for all $x, y, z \in X$. If a BCI-algebra satisfies the identity $0 * x = 0$, then it is called a BCK-algebra.

Definition 1. If $\langle X; *, 0 \rangle$ is a BCI-algebra, A is a non-empty subset of X , and $x * y \in A$ for all $x, y \in A$, then $\langle A; *, 0 \rangle$ is called a subalgebra of $\langle X; *, 0 \rangle$.

Definition 2. [10] A fuzzy set in a set S is a function A from S into $[0, 1]$.

Definition 3. [4] If $\langle X; *, 0 \rangle$ is a BCI-algebra, a fuzzy set A of X is called a fuzzy subalgebra of X if for all $x, y \in X$, it satisfies:

$$A(x * y) \geq A(x) \wedge A(y).$$

Definition 4. [5] $\langle X; *, 0 \rangle$ is a BCI-algebra, a fuzzy subset A of X is called a fuzzy ideal of X if it satisfies:

1. $A(0) \geq A(x), \forall x \in X$,
2. $A(x) \geq A(x * y) \wedge A(y), \forall x, y \in X$.

Definition 5. [6] $\langle X; *, 0 \rangle$ is a BCI-algebra, M is a non-empty set, if there exists a mapping $(m, x) \rightarrow mx$ from $M \times X$ to X which satisfies

$$m(x * y) = (mx) * (my), \forall x, y \in X, m \in M.$$

then M is called a left operator of X , X is called a BCI-algebra with left operator M , or M -BCI-algebra for short.

Proposition 1. Let $\langle X; *, 0 \rangle$ be a M -BCI-algebra, if A is a

fuzzy ideal of it, and $x * y \leq z$, then $A(x) \geq A(y) \wedge A(z)$ for all $x, y, z \in X$.

Definition 6. Let A and B be fuzzy sets of set X , then the direct product $A \times B$ of A and B is a fuzzy subset of $X \times X$, define $A \times B$ by

$$A \times B(x, y) = A(x) \wedge B(y), \forall x, y \in X.$$

Definition 7. [6] Let $\langle X; *, 0 \rangle$ and $\langle \bar{X}; *, 0 \rangle$ be two M -BCI-algebras, if f is a homomorphism from $\langle X; *, 0 \rangle$ to $\langle \bar{X}; *, 0 \rangle$, and $f(mx) = mf(x)$ for all $x \in X, m \in M$, then f is called a homomorphism with operators.

Definition 8. $\langle X; *, 0 \rangle$ is a M -BCI-algebra, let B be a fuzzy set of X , and A be a fuzzy relation of B , if

$$A_B(x, y) = B(x) \wedge B(y) \text{ for all } x, y \in X,$$

then A is called a strong fuzzy relation of B . In the following parts, X always means an M -BCI-algebra unless otherwise specified.

III. FUZZY SUBALGEBRAS OF BCI-ALGEBRAS WITH OPERATORS

Definition 9. If $\langle X; *, 0 \rangle$ is an M -BCI-algebra, A is a non-empty subset of X , and $mx \in A$ for all $x \in A, m \in M$, then $\langle A; *, 0 \rangle$ is called an M -subalgebra of $\langle X; *, 0 \rangle$.

Definition 10. $\langle X; *, 0 \rangle$ is a M -BCI-algebra, A is a fuzzy subalgebra of X , if $A(mx) \geq A(x)$ for all $x \in X, m \in M$, then A is called an M -fuzzy subalgebra of X .

Example 1. If A is an M -fuzzy subalgebra of X , then X_A is an M -fuzzy subalgebra of X , define X_A by

$$X_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1], X_A(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & x \in A \\ 0, & x \notin A. \end{cases}$$

Proof. (1) For all $x, y \in X$, if $x, y \in A$, then $x * y \in A$, therefore

$$X_A(x * y) = 1 \geq X_A(x) \wedge X_A(y),$$

if there exists at least one which does not belong to A between x and y , for example $x \notin A$, thus

$$X_A(x * y) \geq 0 = X_A(x) \wedge X_A(y),$$

therefore X_A is a fuzzy subalgebra of X .

(2) For all $x \in X, m \in M$, if $x \in A$, then $mx \in A$, therefore

$$X_A(mx) = 1 \geq X_A(x),$$

if $x \notin A$, then

$$X_A(mx) \geq 0 = X_A(x),$$

therefore X_A is an M -fuzzy subalgebra of X .

Proposition 3. A is an M -fuzzy subalgebra of X if only if A_t is an M -subalgebra of X , where A_t is a non-empty set, define X_A by

$$A_t = \{x \mid x \in X, A(x) \geq t\}, \forall t \in [0, 1].$$

Proof. Suppose A is an M -fuzzy subalgebra of X , A_t is a non-empty set, $t \in [0, 1]$, then we have

$$A(x * y) \geq A(x) \wedge A(y).$$

If $x \in A_t, y \in A_t$, then

$$A(x) \geq t, A(y) \geq t,$$

thus

$$A(x * y) \geq A(x) \wedge A(y) \geq t,$$

thus we have

$$x * y \in A_t.$$

For all $x \in X, m \in M$, if A is an M -fuzzy subalgebra of X , hence

$$A(mx) \geq A(x) \geq t,$$

thus

$$mx \in A_t,$$

therefore A_t is an M -subalgebra of X . Conversely, suppose A_t is an M -subalgebra of X , then we have $x * y \in A_t$. Let $A(x) = t$, then

$$A(x * y) \geq t = A(x) \geq A(x) \wedge A(y).$$

For all $x \in X, m \in M$, if A_t is an M -subalgebra of X , then we have

$$A(mx) \geq t = A(x),$$

therefore A is an M -fuzzy subalgebra of X .

Proposition 4. Suppose X, Y are M -BCI-algebra, f is a mapping from X to Y , if A is an M -fuzzy subalgebra of

the Y , then $f^{-1}(A)$ is an M -fuzzy subalgebra of X .

Proof. Let $y \in Y$, suppose f is an epimorphism, then there exists x in X , we have $y = f(x)$. If A is an M -fuzzy subalgebra of Y , then we have

$$A(x * y) \geq A(x) \wedge A(y), A(mx) \geq A(x).$$

For all $x, y \in X, m \in M$,

$$(1) f^{-1}(A)(x * y) = A(f(x) * f(y)) \geq A(f(x)) \wedge A(f(y)) = f^{-1}(A)(x) \wedge f^{-1}(A)(y);$$

$$(2) f^{-1}(A)(mx) = A(f(mx)) = A(mf(x)) \geq A(f(x)) = f^{-1}(A)(x).$$

Therefore $f^{-1}(A)$ is an M -fuzzy subalgebra of X .

IV. FUZZY IDEALS OF BCI-ALGEBRAS WITH OPERATORS

Definition 11. $\langle X; *, 0 \rangle$ is an M -BCI-algebra, A is a fuzzy ideal of X , if $A(mx) \geq A(x)$ for all $x \in X, m \in M$, then A is called an M -fuzzy ideal of X .

Example 2. If A is an M -fuzzy ideal of X , then X_A is an M -fuzzy ideal of X , define X_A by

$$X_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1], X_A(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & x \in A \\ 0, & x \notin A \end{cases}$$

Proof. (1) For all $x, y \in X$, if $x, y \in A$, then $x * y \in A$, therefore

$$X_A(0) = 1 \geq X_A(x), X_A(x) = 1 \geq X_A(x * y) \wedge X_A(y),$$

if there exists at least one which does not belong to A between x and y , for example $x \notin A$, thus

$$X_A(0) = 1 \geq X_A(x), X_A(x) \geq X_A(x * y) \wedge X_A(y) = 0,$$

therefore X_A is a fuzzy ideal of X .

(2) For all $x \in X, m \in M$, if $x \in A$, then $mx \in A$, therefore

$$X_A(mx) = 1 \geq X_A(x).$$

If $x \notin A$, then

$$X_A(mx) \geq 0 = X_A(x),$$

therefore X_A is an M -fuzzy ideal of X .

Proposition 5. A is an M -fuzzy ideal of X if and only if A_t is an M -ideal of X , where A_t is non-empty set, define A_t by

$$A_t = \{x \mid x \in X, A(x) \geq t\}, \forall t \in [0, 1].$$

Proof. Suppose A is an M -fuzzy ideal of X , A_t is non-empty set, $t \in [0, 1]$, then we have

$$A(0) \geq A(x) \geq t,$$

thus $0 \in A_t$. If $x * y \in A_t, y \in A_t$, then

$$A(x * y) \geq t, A(y) \geq t,$$

thus

$$A(x) \geq A(x * y) \wedge A(y) \geq t,$$

thus we have

$$x \in A_t.$$

For all $x \in X, m \in M$, if A is an M -fuzzy ideal of X , hence

$$A(mx) \geq A(x) \geq t,$$

thus

$$mx \in A_t,$$

therefore A_t is an M -ideal of X . Conversely, suppose A_t is an M -ideal of X , then we have $0 \in A_t, A(0) \geq t$. Let $A(x) = t$, thus $x \in A_t$, we have

$$A(0) \geq t = A(x),$$

suppose there is no

$$A(x) \geq A(x * y) \wedge A(y),$$

then there exist $x_0, y_0 \in X$, we have

$$A(x_0) < A(x_0 * y_0) \wedge A(y_0),$$

let $t_0 = A(x_0 * y_0) \wedge A(y_0)$, then

$$A(x_0) < t_0 = A(x_0 * y_0) \wedge A(y_0),$$

if $x_0 * y_0 \in A_{t_0}, y_0 \in A_{t_0}$, then we have

$$x_0 \in A_{t_0},$$

then

$$A(x_0) \geq t_0,$$

which is inconsistent with $A(x_0) < t_0 = A(x_0 * y_0) \wedge A(y_0)$,
then we have

$$A(x) \geq A(x * y) \wedge A(y).$$

For all $x \in X, m \in M$, if A is an M -ideal of X , then we have

$$A(mx) \geq t = A(x),$$

therefore A is an M -fuzzy ideal of X .

Proposition 6. Suppose X, Y are M -BCI-algebras, f is a mapping from X to Y , A is an M -fuzzy ideal of Y , then $f^{-1}(A)$ is an M -fuzzy ideal of X .

Proof. Let $y \in Y$, suppose f is an epimorphism, then there exists $x \in X$, we have $y = f(x)$. If A is an M -fuzzy ideal of Y , then we have

$$A(0) \geq A(y) \text{ or } A(f(0)) \geq A(y).$$

For all $x, y \in X, m \in M$,

$$(1) f^{-1}(A)(0) = A(f(0)) = A(0) \geq A(f(x)) = f^{-1}(A)(x);$$

$$(2) f^{-1}(A)(x) = A(f(x)) \geq A(f(x) * f(y)) \wedge A(f(y)) = A(f(x * y)) \wedge A(f(y)) = f^{-1}(A)(x * y) \wedge f^{-1}(A)(y);$$

$$(3) f^{-1}(A)(mx) = A(f(mx)) = A(mf(x)) \geq A(f(x)) = f^{-1}(A)(x).$$

Therefore $f^{-1}(A)$ is an M -fuzzy ideal of X .

V. FUZZY QUOTIENT BCI-ALGEBRAS WITH OPERATORS

Definition 12. Let A be an M -fuzzy ideal of X , for all $a \in X$, fuzzy set A_a on X defined as:

$$A_a : X \rightarrow [0, 1] \\ A_a(x) = A(a * x) \wedge A(x * a), \forall x \in X.$$

Denote $X/A = \{A_a : a \in X\}$.

Proposition 7. Let $A_a, A_b \in X/A$, then $A_a = A_b$ if only if $A(a * b) = A(b * a) = A(0)$.

Proof. Let $A_a = A_b$, then we have $A_a(b) = A_b(b)$, thus

$$A(a * b) \wedge A(b * a) = A(b * b) \wedge A(b * b) = A(0).$$

That is $A(a * b) = A(b * a) = A(0)$. Conversely, suppose that $A(a * b) = A(b * a) = A(0)$. For all $x \in X$, since

$$(a * x) * (b * x) \leq a * b, (x * a) * (x * b) \leq b * a.$$

It follows from Proposition 1 that

$$A(a * x) \geq A(b * x) \wedge A(a * b), A(x * a) \geq A(x * b) \wedge A(b * a).$$

Hence

$$A_a(x) = A(a * x) \wedge A(x * a) \geq A(b * x) \wedge A(x * b) = A_b(x).$$

That is $A_a \geq A_b$. Similarly, for all $x \in X$, since

$$(b * x) * A(a * x) \leq b * a, (x * b) * A(x * a) \leq a * b.$$

It follows from Proposition 1 that

$$A(b * x) \geq A(a * x) \wedge A(b * a), A(x * b) \geq A(x * a) \wedge A(a * b).$$

Hence

$$A_b(x) = A(b * x) \wedge A(x * b) \geq A(a * x) \wedge A(x * a) = A_a(x).$$

That is $A_b \geq A_a$. Therefore, $A_a = A_b$, we complete the proof.

Proposition 8. Let $A_a = A_{a'}, A_b = A_{b'}$, then $A_{a * b} = A_{a' * b'}$.

Proof. Since

$$\begin{aligned} ((a * b) * (a' * b')) * (a * a') &= ((a * b) * (a * a')) * (a' * b') \\ &\leq (a' * b) * (a' * b') \leq b' * b, \\ ((a' * b') * (a * b)) * (b * b') &= ((a' * b') * (b * b')) * (a * b) \\ &\leq (a' * b) * (a * b) \leq a' * a. \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$A((a * b) * (a' * b')) \geq A(a * a') \wedge A(b' * b) = A(0),$$

$$A((a' * b') * (a * b)) \geq A(b * b') \wedge A(a' * a) = A(0).$$

Therefore

$$A((a * b) * (a' * b')) = A((a' * b') * (a * b)) = A(0),$$

it follows from Proposition 7 that $A_{a * b} = A_{a' * b'}$. we completed the proof.

Let A be an M -fuzzy ideal of X . The operation "*" of R/A is defined as:

$$\forall A_a, A_b \in R/A, A_a * A_b = A_{a * b}.$$

By Proposition 7, the above operation is reasonable.

Proposition 9. Let A be an M -fuzzy ideal of X , then

$R/A = \{R/A; *, A_0\}$ is an M – BCI-algebra.

Proof. For all $A_x, A_y, A_z \in R/A$,

$$\begin{aligned} ((A_x * A_y) * (A_x * A_z)) * (A_z * A_y) &= A_{((x*y)*(x*z))*(z*y)} = A_0; \\ (A_x * (A_x * A_y)) * A_y &= A_{(x*(x*y))*y} = A_0; \quad A_x * A_x = A_{x*x} = A_0; \end{aligned}$$

if $A_x * A_y = A_0, A_y * A_x = A_0$, then

$$A_{x*y} = A_0, A_{y*x} = A_0,$$

it follows from Proposition 7 that

$$A(x * y) = A(0), A(y * x) = A(0),$$

hence

$$A_x = A_y.$$

Therefore $R/A = \{R/A; *, A_0\}$ is a BCI-algebra. For all $A_x \in R/A, m \in M$, we define $mA_x = A_{mx}$. Firstly, we verify that $mA_x = A_{mx}$ is reasonable. If $A_x = A_y$, then we verify

$$mA_x = mA_y,$$

that is to verify

$$A_{mx} = A_{my}.$$

We have

$$A(mx * my) = A(m(x * y)) \geq A(x * y) = A(0)$$

and

$$A(my * mx) = A(m(y * x)) \geq A(y * x) = A(0),$$

so we have

$$A(mx * my) = A(my * mx) = A(0),$$

that is, $A_{mx} = A_{my}$. In addition, for all $m \in M, A_x, A_y \in R/A$,

$$m(A_x * A_y) = mA_{x*y} = A_{m(x*y)} = A_{(mx)*(my)} = A_{mx} * A_{my} = mA_x * mA_y.$$

Therefore $R/A = \{R/A; *, A_0\}$ is an M – BCI-algebra.

Definition 13. Let μ be an M – fuzzy subalgebra of X , and A be an M – fuzzy ideal of X , we define a fuzzy set of X/A as:

$$\mu/A : X/A \rightarrow [0, 1], \quad \mu/A(A_i) = \sup_{A_i=A_j} \mu(x), \forall A_i \in X/A.$$

Proposition 10. μ/A is an M – fuzzy subalgebra of X/A .

Proof. For all $A_x, A_y \in X/A$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mu/A(A_x * A_y) &= \mu/A(A_{x*y}) \\ &= \sup_{A_i=A_{x*y}} \mu(z) \geq \sup_{A_i=A_x, A_j=A_y} \mu(s * t) \geq \sup_{A_i=A_x, A_j=A_y} \mu(s) \wedge \mu(t) \\ &= \sup_{A_i=A_x} \mu(s) \wedge \sup_{A_j=A_y} \mu(t) = \mu/A(A_x) \wedge \mu/A(A_y). \end{aligned}$$

For all $m \in M, A_x \in R/A$,

$$\mu/A(A_{mx}) = \sup_{A_{mc}=A_{mx}} \mu(mz) \geq \sup_{A_z=A_x} \mu(z) = \mu/A(A_x).$$

Therefore, μ/A is an M – fuzzy subalgebra of X/A .

VI. DIRECT PRODUCTS OF FUZZY IDEALS IN BCI-ALGEBRAS WITH OPERATORS

Proposition 11. Suppose A and B are M – fuzzy ideals of X , then $A \times B$ is an M – fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$.

Proof. (1) Let $(x, y) \in X \times X$, then

$$A \times B(0, 0) = A(0) \wedge B(0) \geq A(x) \wedge B(y) = A \times B(x, y),$$

thus for all $(x, y) \in X \times X, A \times B(0, 0) \geq A \times B(x, y)$;

(2) For all $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2) \in X \times X$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} A \times B((x_1, x_2) * (y_1, y_2)) &\wedge A \times B(y_1, y_2) \\ &= A \times B(x_1 * y_1, x_2 * y_2) \wedge A \times B(y_1, y_2) \\ &= (A(x_1 * y_1) \wedge B(x_2 * y_2)) \wedge (A(y_1) \wedge B(y_2)) \\ &= (A(x_1 * y_1) \wedge A(y_1)) \wedge (B(x_2 * y_2) \wedge B(y_2)) \\ &\leq A(x_1) \wedge B(x_2) \\ &= A \times B(x_1, x_2), \end{aligned}$$

thus for all $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2) \in X \times X$, we have

$$A \times B(x_1, x_2) \geq A \times B((x_1, x_2) * (y_1, y_2)) \wedge A \times B(y_1, y_2);$$

(3) For all $(x, y) \in X \times X$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} A \times B(m(x, y)) &= A \times B(mx, my) = A(mx) \wedge B(my) \\ &\geq A(x) \wedge B(y) = A \times B(x, y), \end{aligned}$$

thus for all $\forall (x, y) \in X \times X$, we have

$$A \times B(m(x, y)) \geq A \times B(x, y).$$

Therefore $A \times B$ is an M – fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$.

Proposition 12. Suppose A and B are fuzzy sets of X , if

$A \times B$ is an M -fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$, then A or B is an M -fuzzy ideal of X .

Proof. Suppose A and B are M -fuzzy ideals of X , then for all $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2) \in X \times X$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} A \times B(x_1, x_2) &\geq A \times B((x_1, x_2) * (y_1, y_2)) \wedge A \times B(y_1, y_2) \\ &= A \times B((x_1 * y_1), (x_2 * y_2)) \wedge A \times B(y_1, y_2), \end{aligned}$$

if $x_1 = y_1 = 0$, then

$$A \times B(0, x_2) \geq A \times B(0, x_2 * y_2) \wedge A \times B(0, y_2),$$

we have $A \times B(0, x) = A(0) \wedge B(x) = B(x)$, so $B(x_2) \geq B(x_2 * y_2) \wedge B(y_2)$. If $A \times B$ is an M -fuzzy ideal of X , then

$$A \times B(m(x, y)) \geq A \times B(x, y), \forall (x, y) \in X \times X,$$

let $x = 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned} A \times B(m(x, y)) &= A \times B(mx, my) = A(mx) \wedge B(my) = B(my) \\ &\geq A(x) \wedge B(y) = A(0) \wedge B(y) = B(y), \end{aligned}$$

thus we have $B(my) \geq B(y)$ for all $y \in X, m \in M$. Therefore B is an M -fuzzy ideal of X .

Proposition 13. If B is a fuzzy set, A is a strong fuzzy relation A_B of B , then B is a M -fuzzy ideal of X if only if A_B is an M -fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$.

Proof. If B is an M -fuzzy ideals of X , then for all $(x, y) \in X \times X$, we have

$$A_B(0, 0) = B(0) \wedge B(0) \geq B(x) \wedge B(y) = A_B(x, y);$$

for all $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2) \in X \times X$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} A_B(x_1, x_2) &= B(x_1) \wedge B(x_2) \\ &\geq (B(x_1 * y_1) \wedge B(y_1)) \wedge (B(x_2 * y_2) \wedge B(y_2)) \\ &= (B(x_1 * y_1) \wedge B(x_2 * y_2)) \wedge (B(y_1) \wedge B(y_2)) \\ &= A_B(x_1 * y_1, x_2 * y_2) \wedge A_B(y_1, y_2) \\ &= A_B((x_1, x_2) * (y_1, y_2)) \wedge A_B(y_1, y_2); \end{aligned}$$

for all $(x, y) \in X \times X, m \in M$,

$$\begin{aligned} A_B(m(x, y)) &= A_B(mx, my) = B(mx) \wedge B(my) \\ &\geq B(x) \wedge B(y) = A_B(x, y). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, if B is an M -fuzzy ideal of X , then A_B is an M -fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$. Conversely, suppose A_B is an M -fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$, then $\forall (x_1, x_2) \in X \times X$, we have

$$B(0) \wedge B(0) = A_B(0, 0) \geq A_B(x, x) = B(x) \wedge B(x);$$

for all $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2) \in X \times X$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} B(x_1) \wedge B(x_2) &= A_B(x_1, x_2) \\ &\geq A_B((x_1, x_2) * (y_1, y_2)) \wedge A_B(y_1, y_2) \\ &= A_B(x_1 * y_1, x_2 * y_2) \wedge A_B(y_1, y_2) \\ &= (B(x_1 * y_1) \wedge B(x_2 * y_2)) \wedge (B(y_1) \wedge B(y_2)) \\ &= (B(x_1 * y_1) \wedge B(y_1)) \wedge (B(x_2 * y_2) \wedge B(y_2)); \end{aligned}$$

let $x_2 = y_2 = 0$, then

$$B(x_1) \wedge B(0) \geq (B(x_1 * y_1) \wedge B(y_1)) \wedge B(0),$$

if A_B is an M -fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$, then

$$\begin{aligned} A_B(m(x, y)) &\geq A_B(x, y), \forall x, y \in X \times X, m \in M, \\ B(mx) \wedge B(my) &= A_B(mx, my) \geq A_B(x, y) = B(x) \wedge B(y), \end{aligned}$$

if $x = 0$, then

$$B(0) \wedge B(my) = A_B(0, my) \geq A_B(0, y) = B(0) \wedge B(y),$$

namely, $B(my) \geq B(y)$. Therefore B is an M -fuzzy ideal of X .

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